

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

JOURNAL OF TERTIARY AND INDUSTRIAL SCIENCES

A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF THE HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS'
TRAINING COLLEGE, KUMBA

VOLUME 3, NUMBER 2
JULY, 2023

PUBLISHER:
HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS' TRAINING COLLEGE (HTTC)
UNIVERSITY OF BUEA

P.O Box: 249 Buea Road, Kumba
Tel: (+237) 33354691 – Fax: (+237) 33354692
Email: editorinchief@httckumba.com
Website: <http://www.httckumba.com>

EDITORIAL BOARD

Supervision:

Professor Ngomo Horace Manga
University of Buea

Editor-in-Chief:

Prof. Akume Daniel Akume, University of Buea, Cameroon

Associate Editors:

Prof. Ebune B. Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Defang Henry, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Lissouck Daniel, University of Buea, Cameroon

Advisory Editors:

Prof. Tabi Johannes Atemnkeng, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Fonteh Athanasius Amungwa, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Lyonga N. Agnes Ngale, University of Buea, Cameroon

Members of the Editorial Board:

Prof. Yamb Belle Emmanuel, University of Douala, Cameroon
Prof. Ambe Njoh Jonathan, University of South Florida, USA
Prof. John Akande, Bowen University, Nigeria
Prof. Talla Pierre Kisito, University of Dschang, Cameroon
Prof. Rosemary Shafack, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Njimanted Godfrey Forgha, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Prof. Nzalie Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Mouange Ruben, IUT University of Ngaoundere, Cameroon
Prof. Boum Alexander, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Patrick Wanyu Kongnyuy, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Prof. Tchuen Ghyslain, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon
Prof. Rose Frii-Manyi Anjoh, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Foadieng Emmanuel, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Tchinda Rene, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon
Prof. Tabi Pascal Tabot, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Katte Valentine, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Prof. Zinkeng Martina, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Obama Belinga Christian Theophile, University of Ebolowa, Cameroon
Prof. Nkongho Anyi Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Cordelia Givechek Kometa, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Ngouateu Wouagfack Paiguy, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Tchakoutio Alain, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Morfaw Bertrand, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Tamba Gaston, IUT University, Douala, Cameroon
Prof. Koumi Simon, ENS, Ebolowa, University of Yaounde I
Prof. Ajongakoh Raymond, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Ntabe Eric, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Abanda Henry Fonbiyen, Oxford Brookes University, UK
Dr. Luis Alberto Torrez Cruz, University of Witwatersrand, South Africa
Dr. Negou Ernest, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Aloyem Kaze Claude Vidal, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mfombep Priscilla Mebong, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Asoba Gillian, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Bahel Benjamin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Agbortoko Ayuk Nkem, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mouzong Pemi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Orock Fidelis Tanyi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Wanie Clarkson Mvo, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Dr. Molombe Jeff Mbella, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Emmanuel Tata Sunjo, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Ndi Roland Akoh, University of Yaounde I, Cameroon
Dr. Kinfack Juetsa Aubin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Kamda Silapeux Aristide, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Roland Ndah Njoh, University of Buea, Cameroon

Table of Contents

STUDY AND DESIGN OF A FOUR-PORTS HYBRID SOLAR/WIND DC-DC CONVERTER	1
Boukar Miri ¹ , Aloyem Kaze Claude ¹ , Ajamah Ferdinand ¹ , Tchouga Tchao Yannick ² , Ngouateu paigui ¹	
EXPERIMENTAL STUDY AND MULTISCALE NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF CRACKS IN VISCOELASTIC MATERIALS: APPLICATION TO BILINGA (NAUCLEADIDEERRICHI)	18
Mbelle Samuel Bisong* ^{1,2} , Tawe laynde ³ , Francois Njock Bayock ² , Valeriy V. Lepov ^{4,5} , Pierre Kisito Talla 6	
HARVESTING COMPOUNDS THE EFFECT OF WATER DEFICIT ON THE GROWTH AND YIELD OF WATER LEAF [TALINUM TRIANGULARE (JACQ.) WILLD.]	42
Dekoum VM Assaha* ¹ , Awasume Clovis Awasume ¹ , Pascal Tabi Tabot ¹ , Priscilla Mebong Mfombep ¹	
GEOLOCATION AND STUDY OF HOUSEHOLD WELL WATER IN RELATION TO CONTAMINANTS AS HEALTH MAPPING TOOL IN KUMBA, SOUTH WEST REGION, CAMEROON	55
BAHEL Benjamin ^{1,2} , NGWEM Bayiha Blaise ³ , Bate Esame Bate ¹ , NDIVE Martin Molua ¹ , Lissouck Daniel ⁴ , YAMB Emmanuel ³	
ANTHROPOMORPHISM AND GREEN ECONOMY: A STUDY OF JOHN NKEMNGONG NKENGASONG'S ANCESTRAL EARTH	72
Fomin Edward Efuet (Ph.D.)	
HUMAN EVOLUTION IN AFRICA AND GENETIC VARIATION: A GENETIC HISTORIAN'S INTERPRETATION	92
Forka Leypey Mathew Fomine	
THE PRAGMATICS OF CAMEROON ENGLISH	110
Menge Aaron Tabe	
FORMULATION OF A SNAIL-PROTEIN RICH MAIZE BASE WEANING FOOD (NutriPACK)	122
Samuel Metuge ^{1,2,3} , Asoba Gillian Nkeudem ^{1,2} , Tabe Frida Bawak ¹ , Ngede Laura Senge ¹ , Teh Rene Ning ² , Sumbele Irene Ule Ngole ²	
FORMULATION OF A YOGHURT LIKE PRODUCT FROM CORN MILK, SOY BEANS MILK, SKIMMED MILK ENRICHED WITH BANANA FLAVOUR	135
Mateing Cindry, Fidelis Sameh Ebong* ¹ , Asoba. Gilian Mofor ²	

CUSTOMER ATTRACTION AND RETENTION STRATEGIES IN VERY SMALL BUSINESSES: CASE OF BUTCHERIES IN LIMBE, CAMEROON	152
Ndoko Alice Ekoi, Negou Ernest* ² , Nkenganyi Fonkem Marcellus ³	

STUDY AND DESIGN OF A FOUR-PORTS HYBRID SOLAR/WIND DC-DC CONVERTER

By

Boukar Miri¹, Aloyem Kaze Claude¹, Ajamah Ferdinand¹, Tchouga Tchao Yannick²,
Ngouateu paigui¹

1 Department of Renewable Energy, HTTTC Kumba, University of Buea, Buea, Cameroon
2 MIT Company, Germany

Corresponding Author: Aloyem Kaze Claude
Email: kazealoyem@yahoo.fr

Abstract

This research studies and designs a topology for battery charge controller that interfaces four ports: two DC sources ports, one bi-directional storage port and one load port. In order to ensure the continuity in charging the battery and improving the efficiency of energy conversion, two comparators are used respectively to select and to send the higher value of the two voltages to the battery through MOSFETs. To ease the design of the prototype, the system has been broken down into four main parts which are: the input voltage regulation system, the five-volt voltage generator, the battery protection system and peripheral power supply and the battery level control system. The proposed prototype supports an input voltage varying from 12V to 24V and a maximum input of 10A. To finalize the design, the software Autodech Fusion 360 was used to come out with the two dimensions (2D) printed circuit board and the three dimensions (3D) printed circuit board.

Key words: Input voltage regulation system, Five volts voltage regulator, Battery protection system, Battery level control system.

1 Introduction

Electricity generation through conventional energy sources does not only create pollution but also incurs more costs [1]. The main solution to this problem is the development of alternative methods of energy generation through renewable energy sources. With their economical and eco-friendly nature, solar and wind energy sources have emerged nowadays as popular energy sources [1] - [15] despite their intermittency problem. Therefore, it is a challenge to supply uninterrupted and steady power using only solar energy or wind energy [1]. The efficiency and reliability of the system can be improved by combining solar and wind along with a battery. Hybrid energy systems are used as an alternative to conventional energy sources [8]. The aforementioned advantages and the balancing nature of solar irradiation and wind speed have resulted in the solar-wind energy hybrid systems. For the efficient integration of various renewable energy sources, each source is connected to a single converter in a traditional approach, all these sources and converters are coupled to a common DC-link [14] & [16]. Nevertheless, a number of conversion stages leads to more switching losses [16]. Furthermore, due to the intermittent nature of solar and wind energy sources, these converters are not used effectively in the system. Based on the sizing and optimization of the solar-wind hybrid renewable energy system, more research work has been carried out. Multiport converters are widely used in different alternative power generation systems like electric vehicles, hybrid energy storage system, and uninterrupted power supply system [2] - [16]. The designing of a new topology that delivers an integration of solar and wind sources is purpose of this paper. The objective of the design is to realize a four-port hybrid DC-DC converter that uses the higher value of voltages from the two sources to charge a battery.

To ease the designing process, the work has been broken down into four main parts:

- Designing of the input voltage regulation system;
- Sizing of five volts voltage generator;
- Designing of a battery protection system and peripheral power supply;
- Designing of a battery level control system.

2 Literature Review

Large literature exists on DC-DC converters. Firstly, the literature emphasized the three-port topologies which can take only one source of energy. With the improvement of the technology and the development of hybrid systems, the study of the four-port DC-DC converters has become dominant in many studies. Henceforth, Jianwu Zeng in 2020 designed and realized a four-port DC-DC converter for a hybrid wind/solar energy system [9]. This innovation was the extension of the three-port DC-DC converter to a four-port DC-DC converter application without adding extra power devices as illustrated in figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Three-port phase-shift DC-DC converter [9]

This three-port DC-DC converter has been transformed into four port DC-DC converter according to the following figure.

Figure 2: The proposed four-port DC-DC

In another study carried out in 2017, M. Umavathi, Dr. K. Udhayakumar, K. Priyadharshini wrote a paper titled "simulation and analysis of hybrid renewable energy system using an efficient multiport DC-DC converter" [7]. The paper presents a power management of multiple renewable energy sources by using an efficient multiport DC-DC converter. In this research, each port of multiport converter consists of switches, diode and inductor. A single power conversion stage with high-frequency switches is used to regulate the power flow from the load, battery, and solar-wind renewable energy sources. This converter is used to manage the hybrid energy generating system by using bidirectional power flow between battery and load. Maximum power is extracted from solar panel by using a maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithm. The proposed converter has reduced losses, reduced number of power switches and power conversion stages compared to the prevailing standalone hybrid system. The multiport converter is analyzed and validated by using MATLAB simulation software.

Figure 3: Circuit diagram of multiport converter [7]

The gap between this topology and the proposed in our thesis is defined at the level of the selection of the input voltage. In the literature, the mostly proposed topologies are transformers concerned [5] & [15], while in our thesis, we made use of comparators to select the highest value of the input voltage.

3 Methodology

3.1 Global description of the proposed DC-DC converter

Figure 4: Block diagram of the proposed four-port DC-DC converter

As mentioned in the introduction, the proposed DC-DC controller has four main parts as shown in figure 3 above.

The input voltage regulation system (01_solar management) is constituted of two comparators and three MOSFETs and one integrated circuit. It permits to control and regulate the input voltages and chooses the highest to send to the battery.

The five volts voltage generator (02_power generation) is constituted of one integrated circuit and other electronic devices.

The battery protection system and peripheral power supply (03_battery protection and output select and 04_peripherals and USB power management) is constituted of a

circuit composed of electronics devices mounted to protect the battery and the external devices.

The battery level control system (05_battery fuel gauge) is constituted of an integrated circuit which constantly gives the charging or discharging level of the battery. It constitutes the interface of the system with the user.

3.2 Detail description of the proposed DC-DC converter

Here is the description of the four main parts constituting the proposed topology.

3.2.1 Description of input voltage regulation system

This first part of the system permits to regulate and control the input voltages from the sources. The chosen components and their application circuits are described below:

- The input voltage switching system is constituted of the following main elements: two comparators (MCP6241UT-E/OT) denoted IC102 & IC103 and three MOSFETs (AOD 4185) denoted Q101, Q102 and Q103. The comparator IC102 permits to compare the two input voltages and to send the highest to the command. If the solar voltage is too high, Q101 stayed closed while Q102 and Q103 are open to allow the solar voltage to charge the battery, and vice versa. The mounting circuits of these components is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 5: Command circuit of input voltages

The two different voltages are activated in function of the value that the comparator below sends to the gates of MOSFETs Q101 and Q103. This comparator is connected to the switching system (MOSFETs Q101 and Q103) through the voltage divider bridge.

Figure 6: Comparator 1: circuit activator of MOSFETs Q101 and Q103

This circuit is obtained with the following equations using the voltage divider method:

$$V_{IN-} = \frac{R_{118} \times V_e}{R_{115} + R_{118}} \quad \text{where, } V_e = 24V, \text{ hence } V_{IN-} = 3,93V \quad (1)$$

And

$$V_{IN+} = \frac{R_{117} \times V_s}{R_{116} + R_{117}} \quad \text{where, } V_s = 21V, \text{ hence } V_{IN+} = 3,44V \quad (2)$$

If $V_{IN+} < V_{IN-}$ we will have $V_{OUT} = \text{Drive 1} = +5V$, then the MOSFET Q103 will be forward biased and the functioning voltage of the system will be the one of the wind turbine.

If $V_{IN+} > V_{IN-}$ we will have $V_{OUT} = \text{Drive 1} = \text{GND}$, then the MOSFET Q101 will be forward biased and the functioning voltage of the system will be the one of the solar panel.

To control the functioning voltage, we use the MOSFET Q104 (in figure 9) which is commanded by the comparator in figure 7. This other comparator is connected to comparator 1 and to the battery protection.

Figure 7: Comparator 2: circuit activator of MOSFET Q104

This circuit is obtained by using the following equations:

$$V_{IN-} = \frac{R_{122} \times V_s}{R_{119} + R_{122}} \quad \text{where } V_s = 21V, \text{ hence } V_{IN-} = 3,44V \quad (3)$$

And

$$V_{IN+} = \frac{R_{121} \times V_{BAT+}}{R_{120} + R_{121}} \quad \text{where } V_{BAT+} = 13V, \text{ hence } V_{IN+} = 2,13V \quad (4)$$

If $V_{IN+} < V_{IN-}$ we will have $V_{OUT} = \text{Drive 1} = +5V$, then the MOSFET Q104 will be forward biased and the battery voltage will be less than the voltage from the selector (solar or wind); and the battery will be charged normally.

If $V_{IN+} > V_{IN-}$ we will have $V_{OUT} = \text{Drive 1} = GND$, then the MOSFET Q104 will be blocked and the battery voltage is higher than the voltage from the selector (solar or wind turbine). Then, the voltage from the source will be sent directly to the output.

- Charging regulation component (charger): this part of the circuit ensures the battery charging regulation. To perform this work, the integrated circuit CN3767 with the following characteristics was used: wide input voltage (6.6V to 30V), charging current (4A), High PWM switching frequency (300KHz) and operating ambient temperature ($-40^{\circ}C$ to $+85^{\circ}C$). It permits the solar panel/wind turbine to generate a voltage (VBAT) which varies between **13.55V** and **14.8V** to charge the battery. This component is represented by the following picture:

Figure 8: Representation of CN3767 integrated circuit [16]

After a minacious selection of components associated to the CN3767 such as gate driver, input and output capacitors, MOSFET and diode, the following circuit diagram was designed:

Figure 9: Charging block diagram using CN3767 integrated circuit

3.2.2 Description of five volts voltage generator

To be able to supply the different integrated circuits, there was a need to provide a DC power supply that can take in between the voltage of the battery of 13V.

After some research, it was decided to use the TPS5450DDAR which is a step-down voltage converter with an output voltage of 1.2V, an output current of 5A and an input voltage of 5V. It has 9 pins as presented in the figure below:

Figure 10: Pin configuration of the TPS5450DDAR [18]

The TPS5450 device is a 36V, 5A, step-down converter with an integrated high-side MOSFET. This device is typically used to convert a higher DC voltage to a lower DC voltage with a maximum available output current of 5A.

The typical application circuit of the TPS5450 is shown below:

Figure 11: Typical application circuit of the TPS5450DDAR

To begin the design process of TPS5450DDAR, few parameters are required. These requirements are typically determined at the system levels.

Tableau 1: Design parameters of the TPS5450DDAR [17]

Design parameters	Example value
Input voltage range	10V to 31V
Output voltage	5V
Input ripple voltage	400mV
Output ripple voltage	30mV
Output current rating	5A
Operating frequency	500Hz

3.2.3 Description of the Battery protection system

This system is constituted of components such as diodes, resistors, fuse, transistors and switches. The circuit diagram of the battery protection system and the output of the system is presented on the following figure:

Figure 12: Battery protection system and peripheral power supply

The principle of operation of the battery protection system is as follow: at the input of the circuit, there is the protection circuit that is responsible for blocking the current in case of inversion of terminals during the connection. When the solar panel/wind turbine voltage is higher than the battery voltage, the voltage VBAT will be the one found at the OUT 12V. If the battery voltage is higher than the solar panel/wind turbine voltage, we will have the BAT+ voltage coming from the battery at OUT 12V. This circuit is thus highlighted to be able to make the management of the solar panel/wind turbine voltage and that of the battery according to their values.

3.2.4 Description Battery level control system

For this circuit, the CN1185 integrated circuit was used. A CN1185 is a low-power four-channel voltage monitoring chip which consumes only $7.3\mu\text{A}$ current and it is very suitable for monitoring a battery's voltage. The operating supply voltage range is 2.7V-6V, the guaranteed output voltage valid to 1.2V and the operating temperature range between -40°C to $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$. The device contains four voltage comparators. Each comparator's positive input receives on-chip voltage reference. It can be used to monitor four different voltage sources or a voltage source for monitoring different grades. Users can choose the logic input to select the comparator threshold and set the comparator hysteresis. The existent hysteresis of comparator is to cancel the power due to interference or noise caused by the comparator output instability. Because the user can set the comparator threshold and hysteresis, CN1185 is suitable for rough monitoring battery applications. To facilitate work on the same system with different voltage chip applications, CN1185 is open-drain output. Also, to ensure an instant system power-on work, CN1185 has 7.5ms (minimum) start time and the comparator output is at high impedance state in the start time.

Figure 13: Representation of CN1185 [17]

The typical application circuit of the CN1185 is represented in the figure below:

Figure 14: Typical application circuit of CN1185 [17]

In this prototype, the CN1185 permits to command the LEDs which indicate the real level of charging or discharging of a battery.

The electronic components associated to CN1185 comparator are:

- ✓ Resistor divider network design constituted of resistors R401, R402, R403, R404 and R405 shown in figure 12 below. In the design of the resistor divider network of resistor values, we first need to determine R401, R402, R403, R404 and R405 current consumption. The design steps are as follows:

- Determine $R401 + R402 + R403 + R404 + R405$ value;

- Calculate the value of resistor R405

$$R405 = \left(\frac{V_{ref}}{V_{th4}} \right) \times (R401 + R402 + R403 + R404 + R405)$$

- Calculate the value of resistor R404

$$R404 = \left(\frac{V_{ref}}{V_{th4}} \right) \times (R401 + R402 + R403 + R404 + R405) - R405$$

- Calculate the value of resistor R403

$$R403 = \left(\frac{V_{ref}}{V_{th4}} \right) \times (R401 + R402 + R403 + R404 + R405) - R405 - R404$$

- Calculate the value of resistor R402

$$R402 = \left(\frac{V_{ref}}{V_{th4}} \right) \times (R401 + R402 + R403 + R404 + R405) - R405 - R404 - R403$$

- Calculate the value of resistor R401

$$R401 = (R401 + R402 + R403 + R404 + R405) - R405 - R404 - R403 - R402$$

- ✓ Monitoring of voltage greater than 6V: the power system can be 2.7V to 6V already or the voltage can be monitored or regulated through the step-down power.
- ✓ Filter capacitor: generally, the CN1185 does not require power supply filter capacitor. However, if the CN1185 work in a relatively strong noise or electromagnetic interference environment, or be monitored power itself superimposed clutter, then we can add a 0.1uF capacitor between VDD and GND to effectively filter out interferences. If the monitored power supply voltage transients are relatively strong, the filter capacitor value should be larger. From the comparator's negative input to ground plus, a 1nF capacitor can effectively improve the noise immunity of CN1185.

From this information, the following circuit of our system can be wired.

Figure 15: Battery level control system circuit

3.3 Assembling of the prototype

After describing the different parts of the prototype, the wiring was proceeded following the stages below:

- The input voltage regulation system, made up of two comparators and the charging regulator is connected to the five-volt generator which supplies the switches and the other components.

- The five-volt generator is then connected to the battery level control system, which gives information of the charging level of the battery.
- The input voltage regulation system is connected to the battery protection system and the peripheral power supply which constitutes the output system.
- Finally, the five-volt voltage generator is connected to the battery protection system and the peripheral.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Results

After realizing the circuits of the four main parts of the proposed prototype, using the software Autodesk Fusion 360, we came out with the following 2D PCB (figure 15) circuit and 3D PCB (figure 16) circuit of the prototype.

By respecting the assembling procedures announced above, Autodesk Fusion 360 permitted the electronic cards below. On these cards, one can notice the presence of additional materials like stain which ensures the fixation of different materials on the card and heat sink presented in black color. Made up of aluminum, the heat sink permits to reduce the heating of the MOSFETs.

Figure 16: 2D printed circuit board (PCB)

Figure 17: 3D printed circuit board (PCB)

4.2 Discussion

The results presented above are in line with the objective of the study which is the design of a four-ports solar/wind charge controller. This prototype, compared to the one on the market, can permit to charge a battery continuously and efficiently, improving its lifespan simultaneously. According to the configuration and the functioning of this prototype, it can be affirmed that it is the extension of a three-port DC-DC converter. The difference made with the three-port DC-DC converter is that, input voltage regulation system contains a switching system which enables to select the highest input voltage to charge the battery, increasing by the occasion the charging speed.

Compared to the existing four-port DC-DC converters, this prototype automatically selects the highest input voltage while the existing ones do not switch automatically to select an input voltage.

5 Conclusions

The materials and components used to build up the prototype are summarized in the table below:

Table 2: Materials and components used to realize the prototype

N°	Main parts	Components associated	Number
1	Input voltages regulation system	Resistors	22
		Capacitors	10
		Inductance	1
		Diodes	7
		Transistors	6
		Jumpers	2
		Comparators	2
		Integrated circuit (CN3767)	1
2	Five volts voltage generator	Resistors	4
		Capacitors	6
		Inductance	1
		Diode	1
		Integrated circuit (TPS5450DDAR)	1
3	Battery protection system and peripheral power supply	Resistors	6
		Diodes	5
		Fuse	1
		Transistors	4
		Jumper	2
4	Battery level control system	Resistors	14
		Capacitors	2
		Diodes	4
		Jumper	1
		Integrated circuit (CN1185)	1

To realize the proposed prototype, we used in total 10 transistors, 46 resistors, 18 capacitors, 2 inductances, 17 diodes (all types), 2 comparators and 1 fuse. Those components are connected to the integrated circuits as demanded by the manufacturers.

The outstanding features of the proposed charge controller are:

- MPPT four-ports solar/wind charge controller;
- Input voltage range: 12V-24V;
- Output voltage: 12V;
- External battery charging: 12V

The designed prototype is realizable and functionable. Its major advantage is its ability to charge a battery continuously, efficiently and at high speed, therefore increasing its lifespan. The lifespan of a battery charged by this prototype is multiplied by two, since it can be charged every day and night by either the solar panel or the wind turbine.

6 Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge the professor **AKUME Daniel AKUME**, Director of HTTTC Kumba for his encouragements and support.

7 References

- [1] M. Umavathi, Dr. K. Udhayakumar, K. Priyadharshini, "simulation and analysis of hybrid renewable energy system using an efficient multiport dc-dc converter" *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*, Anna University, Chennai, 2017
- [2] H. Tao, A. Kotsopoulos, J. Duarte, and M. Hendrix, "Family of multiport bidirectional DC-DC converters," in *IEE Proc. Electric Power Appl.*, vol. 153, no. 3, pp. 451-458, May 2006.
- [3] H. Wu, K. Sun, R. Chen, H. Hu, and Y. Xing, "Full-bridge three-port converters with wide input voltage range for renewable power systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 27, no. 9, pp. 3965-3974, Sept. 2012.
- [4] J. Zeng, W. Qiao and L. Qu, "An isolated three-port bidirectional DC-DC converter for photovoltaic systems with energy storage," *IE*
- [5] V. Jakka, A. Shukla, and G. Demetriades, "Dual-transformer-based asymmetrical tripleport active bridge (DT-ATAB) isolated DC-DC converter," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 64, no. 6, pp. 4549-4560, June 2017.
- [6] S. Bull, "Renewable energy today and tomorrow," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 89, no. 8, pp. 1216- 1226, Aug 2001.
- [7] <https://www.engadget.com/2017/10/04/solar-power-global-renewable-energy/>. (visited on July 14th, 2022 at 10h05'am).
- [8] Jianwu Zeng, Jiahong Ning, Taesic Kim, and Vincent Winstead "Modeling and Control of a Four-port DC-DC Converter for a Hybrid Energy System" *IEEE APEC – IEEE Applied Power Electronic Conference and Exposition*, Los angeles, USA, March, 2019.
- [9] Ning, J. (2020). A four-port DC-DC converter for a hybrid wind/solar energy system [Master's thesis, Minnesota State University, Mankato]. Cornerstone: A Collection of Scholarly and Creative Works for Minnesota State University, Mankato.
- [10] Qian, Zhijun, "Modeling And Design Of Multi-port DC/DC Converters" (2010). *Electronic Theses and Dissertations*, 2004-2019. 1543.
- [11] K. Itoh, M. Ishigaki, N. Yanagizawa, S. Tomura, and T. Umeno, "Analysis and design of a multi-port converter using a magnetic coupling inductor technique," in *Proc. Energy Convers. Congr. Expo.*, Sept. 2013, pp. 4713-4718.
- [12] W. Li, C. Xu, H. Luo, Y. Hu, X. He, and C. Xia, "Decoupling-controlled triport composited DC/DC converter for multiple energy interface," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Electron.*, vol. 62, no. 7, pp. 4504-4513, July 2015
- [13] Z. Ding, C. Yang, Z. Zhang, C. Wang, and S. Xie, "A novel soft-switching multiport bidirectional DC-DC converter for hybrid energy storage system," *IEEE Trans. Power Electron.*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 1595-1609, April 2014.
- [14] H. Tao, A. Kotsopoulos, J.L. Duarte, M.A.M Hendrix, "Multi-Input Bidirectional DC-DC Converter Combining DC-link and Magnetic-coupling for Fuel Cell Systems," in *Proc. IEEE Industry Applications Conf.*, 2005, pp. 2021- 2028.

- [15] Y. M. Chen, Y. C. Liu, and F. Y. Wu, "Multi-input DC/DC Converter Based On the Multi-winding Transformer for Renewable Energy Applications" *IEEE Trans. Industrial Applications*, vol. 38, pp. 1096 - 1104, August 2002.
- [16] Z. Qian, O. Abdel-Rahman, J. Reese, H. Al-Atrash, I. Batarseh, "Dynamic Analysis of Three-Port DC/DC Converter for Space Applications," in *Proc. IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conf.*, 2009, pp.28 - 34.
- [17] <http://www.consonance-elec.com/> (visited on February 16th, 2023 at 9pm)
- [18] <http://www.ti.com> (visited on February 19th, 2023 at 10pm)